

Screening Survey for Observational Secret Management Tools Study

The following survey will act as a screening survey for prospective participants. Any responses involving tool experience will be collected as part of research only if the prospective participant qualifies, consents and is chosen to participate.

What is your Age?

(You must be older than 18 years old to participate in this study. If you prefer not to answer, enter a number greater than 150)

Are you able to participate in a one hour hands-on observational study in English at a conversational and/or fluent level?

Yes

No

Very briefly, how much experience, either at the professional or graduate academic level, do you have in managing secrets within software development or coding projects (i.e. specific practices you performed to manage your secrets for your projects, the organizations in which you managed secrets at, projects you worked on managing secrets, etc)

How did you learn to manage secrets?

University Courses

- Textbooks/Academic Books
- Research Papers
- Tutorial Books
- Online courses (e.g., coursera)
- Informal Community Discussion (Discord, Slack)
- Forum-based platforms (Reddit)
- QA platforms (Kaggle, Stackoverflow)
- Company-Provided Trainings
- Company-Sponsored Conferences
- Other (Please Specify)

Do you have prior experience using Linux or MacOs based commands in a command line interface?

- Yes
- No

Do you have prior experience coding in Python and executing coding files with Python run commands?

- Yes
- No

Do you have a general understanding of what environment variables are within software development and coding?

- Yes
- No

Are you able to travel to our research campus at North Carolina State University to participate in-person for the study?

- Yes

No

Contact Info

Thank you for completing this screening survey! We will contact you with further instructions if your responses align with our research interests. Please write your full name to finish the survey.

What is your full name?

Please enter your email address

